

Cupric Complexes of Some Ortho-hydroxy Azo-dyes: Part I.

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The paper deals with the study of the cupric complexes of some substituted hydroxy azo-dyes, viz., 6-hydroxy-azobenzene-3-methyl-4'-sulphonic acid (abbreviated to 3-Me-4'-sulphodye), 4'-Me-3-sulpho dye and 3-sulpho dye.

This investigation has been carried out to study the effects of a methyl and a sulphonic acid group on the pK_a values of the dyes and the stability constants of their cupric complexes.

The method of synthesis of the dyes and the dye-intermediate *p*-sulphophenol has been described in this paper. The composition of the cupric complexes were investigated conductometrically and confirmed spectrophotometrically. Jobs' method of continuous variations and mono-variation methods established the formation of 1:2 (ML_2) as the highest cupric complex.

The values of pK_a are 8.75, 7.72 and 7.53 respectively. The values of $\log K_1$ are found to be 6.14, 6.07 and 6.08 and those of $\log K_2$ are 4.61, 4.43 and 4.42 respectively. The stability constants have been calculated by using Janseen's method with suitable modifications.

This investigation has been carried out to study the effects of a methyl and a sulphonic acid group on the pK_a values of the dyes and the stability constants of their cupric complexes. The effects of various substituents on pK_a values of ligands and on the stability constants of the metal chelates can be studied by having various substituents in the same position and by putting the same substituents in different positions.

The composition of the highest cupric complex formed, as determined by different methods, is 1:2 (ML_2). The values of pK_a are 8.75, 7.72 and 7.53 respectively. The values of $\log K_1$ are 6.14, 6.07 and 6.08 and those of $\log K_2$ are 4.61, 4.43 and 4.42 respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

As none of these structurally related dyes were available, these were synthesised. For this, sulphanilic acid (AnalaR), redistilled *p*-toluidine (Riedel) or redistilled aniline (M & B) was diazotised and then coupled with *p*-sulphophenol or freshly distilled *p*-cresol (B.D.H.) in alkaline medium.

To obtain *p*-sulphophenol, 0.1 M of sulphanilic acid (A.R.) was first diazotised. The diazonium compound was then hydrolysed by heating it with 8 ml. of conc. HCl (0.1M) on a waterbath between 50—60° for about 2 hr. Temperature was then gradually raised to 70° and kept at this temperature for another 2 hr. to ensure complete hydrolysis. To remove the unhydrolysed diazonium compound, it was boiled off to a small volume in a shallow basin over a waterbath. Before coupling, the *p*-sulphophenol was made alkaline by adding 8 g. of NaOH and 15.9 g. of Na_2CO_3 (A.R.). No red colour should develop. If red colour develops, indicating self-coupling, the sample has to be discarded.

Just before coupling, excess of nitrous acid was destroyed by adding about 0.2 g. of urea (B.D.H.). The coupled product was kept in dark and cooled at room temperature for a few hours. The solution was heated on a waterbath and acidified with 0.05 M of conc. HCl and a little glacial acetic acid (AnalaR). The dye was separated as its barium salt and then converted into its mono-sodium salt by Na_2SO_4 . It was then recrystallised repeatedly from alcohol-water mixture and dried in an oven and ultimately over P_2O_5 . Dyes were analysed for their nitrogen and sulphur contents. The percentage of N_2 in 3-Me-4'-sulpho dye, 4'-Me-3-sulpho dye and 3-sulpho dye was found to be 8.90, 8.90 and 9.31 respectively and the percentage of sulphur was found to be 10.11, 10.10 and 10.62 respectively.

Stock solutions of the dyes as sodium sulphonate ($M/200$) were prepared in double distilled water by treating the dye with one equivalent of sodium carbonate (AnalaR). Cupric chloride (AnalaR, B.D.H.) was used to prepare $M/200$ stock solution.

Composition of the Complex: (1) Conductivity measurements were carried out at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. and both Job's method of continuous variation and the monovariation method, were used at three different concentrations, viz. $M/500$, $M/600$ and $M/800$, for determining the composition of the complexes.

For Job's method of continuous variation, the plots of ΔC , or the deviation of conductance from additivity against the volume fraction of the ligand, x , showed a maxima at $x=0.67$, indicating the formation of a 1:2 (ML_2) complex.

In the monovariation method, V ml of the ligand solution were mixed with 5ml. of the metal ion in solution of same concentration and the volume made to 20 ml. with distilled water. V varied from 0.0 ml. to 15.0 ml., and the plots of the conductance of the mixtures against V show two clear slopes. The lowest slope is obtained when V is 1 to 5 ml. when mostly 1:1 (ML) complex is being formed. The slope, however, becomes steeper for values of V between 5 and 10 ml. showing the formation of 1:2 (ML_2) complex and finally the steepest slope (almost straight) is obtained for values of V above 10 ml. showing thereby that no higher complexes like ML_3 , ML_4 etc. are being formed.

(2) For the Job's method of continuous variation by spectrophotometer, equimolar solutions used were $M/10,000$. The $p\text{H}$ values of the ligand and the mixtures were adjusted by $M/10$ and $M/100$ NaOH solutions so that they were about one unit above the pK_a values of the dyes and that precipitation did not occur. For 3-Me-4'-sulpho dye the $p\text{H}$ used was 9.0 ± 0.05 and for 4'-Me-3-sulpho dye and 3-sulpho dye it was $8.0 + 0.05$.

The analytical wavelength¹, i.e. the wavelength at which ΔA is maximum, was found by trial. An idea of this wavelength could be had from the absorption curves of the dye ion, the dye molecule and the cupric complex (ML_2), which were taken with $M/20,000$ solutions prepared by mixing 5 ml. of $M/1000$ dye solution, 10ml. of $M/10$ NaOH solution or HCl acid (AnalaR) and making up the total volume to 100 ml. with distilled water. Absorbance curve of the cupric complex was also drawn at a $p\text{H}$ of ($pK_a - 1.0$). Two wavelengths were found out such that, at one of the wavelengths, absorbance of the mixture was

1, C. F. Hiskey, *Anal. Chem.*, 1949, **21**, 1440.

more than that of the dye, and at the other wavelength, the absorbance of the mixture was less than that of the dye.

The method of continuous variation, when applied spectrophotometrically, also shows a sharp peak at $x=0.67$, when ΔA is plotted against x , the volume fraction of the ligand. This further confirms the formation of a 1:2 complex.

Determination of the pK_a values of the ligands: The pK_a values were obtained from the relation :

$$pK_a = pH + \log \frac{A_I - A}{A - A_M} \quad \dots \quad (E-1)$$

where A_I and A_M are the absorbances of the ion and the molecule of the ligand and A that of a series of mixtures of ions and molecules.

Applicability of Beer's law was first verified for both ionised and nonionised forms of the ligands. For ionised form solution of dyes used ranged between 4×10^{-5} and 6×10^{-5} M in 0.01 N NaOH and for unionised form same concentrations of the dye were prepared in 0.01 N formic acid. It was found that the Beer's law was applicable and the value of A_I for $2 \times 10^{-5} M$ was found to be 0.550 and A_M for the unionised form of the same concentration was 0.048, for 3-Me-4'-sulpho dye. The molar extinctions, E_I and E_M , of the ion and the molecule were found to be 10995 and 955 respectively. Table I gives data for 3-Me-4'-sulpho dye.

TABLE I

Wavelength = 498 m μ ;				slit = 0.01 mm.		
		A_I		A_M		
V(ml.)	A	A/V	Average	A'	A'/V	Average
2.0	0.446	0.2230		0.038	0.0190	
2.2	0.493	0.2241		0.042	0.0191	
2.5	0.544	0.2176	0.2199	0.048	0.0192	0.0191
2.7	0.591	0.2187		0.052	0.0192	
3.0	0.648	0.2160		0.057	0.0190	

To determine the absorbances, A , of a series of mixtures of the ions and the molecules (Eqn. E-1), 2.5 ml. of $M/500$ ligand were mixed with 10 ml. of $M/10$ KH_2PO_4 or boric acid or a mixture of these two and varying amounts of $M/10$ NaOH and making up the total volume to 100 ml. with distilled water, in order to obtain $M/20,000$ dye solution buffered at the desired pH around 7, 8 and 9. The absorbances of these mixtures were noted at the analytical wavelength, whence approximate pK_a values were calculated.

To determine the exact pK_a values, 10 ml. of suitable buffer was mixed with varying amounts of $M/10$ NaOH, 2.5 ml. of $M/500$ ligand solution and distilled water to make up the total volume to 100 ml. The amount of NaOH was adjusted such that the pH was equal to approximate pK_a , approximate $pK_a \pm 0.2$, approximate $pK_a \pm 0.4$ and approximate $pK_a \pm 0.6$, respectively.

From the absorbances of these solutions seven values of pK_a were obtained. The average gave the exact pK_a value. Table II gives data for 3-Me-4'-sulpho dye.

TABLE II

		$A_I = 0.550$;	$A_M = 0.048$		
		wavelength = 498 m μ	;	slit = 0.01mm.		
Sr. No.	pH	Absorbance		Approximate pK_a		
1	7.8	0.157				
2	8.5	0.241		8.7		
3	9.1	0.370				
Sr. No.	pH	Absorbance		pK_a	Mean pK_a	
1	8.2	0.162		8.73		
2	8.3	0.178		8.76		
3	8.5	0.240		8.71		
4	8.7	0.288		8.74		8.75
5	8.85	0.304		(8.83)		
6	9.05	0.368		8.81		
7	9.30	0.440		8.75		

Stability constants of the cupric complexes: Stability constants have been calculated using Janseen's method² with suitable modification.

The series of solutions were prepared by mixing 10 ml. of $0.5 \times 10^{-4}M$ dye solution with varying volumes of the metal salt solutions of appropriate concentrations and making up the total volume to 100 ml. with distilled water such that T_M/T_L could be varied continuously from 1/100 to 500/100, i.e. from 0 to 500 stepwise. This enabled the formation of both the complexes, ML_2 and ML . Initially, when $T_L \gg T_M$ only the higher complex ML_2 is almost exclusively formed. This range was used for the determination of the molar extinction coefficient, E_2 , of the 1:2 complex. Ultimately when $T_M \gg T_L$ (highest possible values without causing precipitation) only the lower complex, ML , is almost exclusively formed. This range was used for the determination of the molar extinction coefficient, E_1 , of the 1:1 complex.

Before noting the absorbances of the mixtures, the pHs were adjusted to about one unit lower than the pK_a values of the dyes very carefully.

E_L , the molar extinction coefficient of the dye, is calculated from the absorbances when no metal has been added, i.e. when $V=0$ ml. For this a series of values of absorbance for varying concentrations of the dye at the pH of work were taken and the average E_L was worked out by Beer's Law.

In between the above two extremes, both the complexes are formed in varying proportions. This range has, therefore, been used for the determination of the stability constants. $\log K_1$ has been determined from the lower half of this range and $\log K_2$ from the upper half.

Log K_1 has been calculated from the following relation:

$$K_1 = \frac{(A - E_L T_L) (E_I - E_L) \times F}{(E_I - E_L) T_M + E_L \cdot T_L - A(E_I T_L - A)} \quad \dots \quad (E - 2)$$

where F , the conversion factor, is equal to $C_L/[L]$, which in its turn is equal to $1 + K_{H^+} \cdot [H]$, C_L being the concentration at equilibrium of the ligand not bound in a complex with the metal ion, i.e. $C_L = L + HL + H_2L + \dots$

and $[L]$ is the concentration at equilibrium of the free ligand, L , not bound to metal or hydrogen ions.

Preliminary values of E_I and K_1 obtained have been subjected to a process of successive approximation.

Log K_2 has been calculated using the following relation:

$$K_2 = \frac{[ML_2] \cdot F}{[ML] \cdot C_L} \quad \dots \quad (E - 3)$$

Following table, table III, gives full data for one of the dyes investigated, viz. 3-Me-4'-sulpho dye.

TABLE III

Cupric Complex of 3-Me-4'-sulpho dye

$pK_a = 8.75$; $pH = 7.75$

$E_L = 1940$; $E_I = 6708$

wavelength = 498 m μ ; slit = 0.01 mm.

Sr. No	$T_M \times 10^6$	Absorbance	
1	0.0	0.097	E_2
2	0.5	0.104	17880
3	1.0	0.111	17890
4	2.0	0.120	15360 x
5	15.0	0.170	Log K_2
6	20.0	0.187	4.67
7	25.0	0.205	4.56
8	30.0	0.222	4.54
9	60.0	0.268	4.66
10	70.0	0.278	log K_1
11	80.0	0.288	6.14
12	90.0	0.298	6.11
13	100.0	0.308	6.15
14	250.0	0.312	6.15

Average value of log $K_1 = 6.135$

„ „ „ $K_2 = 4.607$

The following table, table IV, gives the values of pK_a , $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ for the three dyes investigated:

TABLE IV

Sr. No.	Dye	pK_a	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$
1	3-Me-4'-sulpho dye	8.75	6.14	4.61
2	4'-Me-3-sulpho dye	7.72	6.07	4.43
3	3-sulpho dye	7.53	6.08	4.42

DISCUSSION

Variation of pK_a with the nature and position of the substituent: Methyl group is known to be a σ - and π - electron donor. Hence the substitution of a methyl group would increase the electron density on the phenolic oxygen atom and consequently decrease the extent of ionisation, i.e. increase the pK_a of the ligand. The pK_a of the unsubstituted dye (3-sulpho dye) is 7.53, while those of both the methyl dyes are higher (viz. 7.72 and 8.75); that of the 3-methyl dye being the highest. Further, it is observed that if a methyl group is present in the phenol at position 3, its effect is most intense. If it is present in the amine ring at position 4', its effect on the pK_a is much less.

Sulphonic acid group, on the other hand, is known to be a σ - and π - electron acceptor. Hence the substitution of sulphonic acid group would decrease the electron density and, therefore, would increase the extent of ionisation, i.e. would decrease the pK_a of the ligand. Above expectation is completely borne out from the pK_a values obtained. The pK_a of the 3-sulpho dye is lowest (7.53); those of the methyl dyes are higher, and that of the 3-Me-4'-sulpho dye being the highest (8.75). This shows that the pK_a lowering effect from position 3 is much more than the pK_a elevating effect of the methyl group from the distant position 4', distance being measured from the phenolic oxygen. Similarly, when the electron attracting sulpho group is placed at 4' and electron repelling methyl group is placed at 3, the pK_a lowering effect of the distant sulpho group becomes much less than the pK_a elevating effect of the methyl group. Thus it is observed that not only the nature of the groups but also their positions, whether present in the phenolic ring or in the amine ring, have a direct bearing on the pK_a values.

Correlation of the stability constants and pK_a : A close relationship between ligand basicity (pK_a) and complex stability ($\log K$ or $\log \beta_2$) is well expected. While some³ have given a linear relationship between $\log K$ (H) and $\log \beta_2$, others⁴ have shown that linear plots are only very rough. From table IV, it is observed that a rough linear relationship between $\log K$ (H) and stability constants is obtained. 3-Me-4'-sulpho dye with highest pK_a (8.75) gives highest stability constants ($\log K_1=6.14$ and $\log K_2=4.61$). The stability constants of the cupric complexes of the remaining two dyes are almost equal. This shows that the distant methyl group has hardly any effect on the stabilities of the complexes. Slightly higher than expected stability of the complex of 3-sulpho dye with cupric ion can possibly be rationalised on the basis that the electron acceptor sulpho group can better promote the π -bonding with $d\pi$ -donor Cu(II) from the para position 3.

3. E. Larsson, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1934, **A169**, 215.

4. J. C. Tomkinson and R. J. P. Williams, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 201.

From table IV, it is observed that $\log K_2$ values are lower than $\log K_1$ values by approximately 1.5 units. This shows that in this case not only the statistical effect (which gives the value of $\log K_1 - \log K_2 = 0.60$ units) is to be considered but here the electrostatic effect⁵ also becomes important ($\log K_1 - \log K_2 = 1.5$ units).

If we consider stepwise formation of 1:2 cupric complex, $ML_2, E_{0,1}$, the work done, will have a rather large value since Cu^{2+} and L^{2-} have to be brought together, while the lower 1:1 complex, ML , is being first formed. The resultant 1:1 complex will now have zero charge. Now when the higher complex, ML_2 , is being formed by the union of the zero charge being ML and L^{2-} , $E_{1,2}$ would be very much less than $E_{0,1}$. This explains why $\log K_2$ is lower than $\log K_1$.

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Received, August 8, 1967.